

EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM MODELS IN ENHANCING STUDENT ENGAGEMENT AND LEARNING OUTCOMES AT NIS, CHEMISTRY AND BIOLOGY, SHYMKENT, KAZAKHSTAN: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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INTRODUCTION

In today's educational system, the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning is rapidly becoming one of the most prominent trends that can be found.

The digitalization of society means that the demands placed on employee skills increase or change throughout their careers (OECD, 2019) {1}. It is owing to the rise of technology as well as the need to modernize the educational process. To meet the demands of a digital society, educational institutions are expected to provide greater flexibility and individualization so that learners have the opportunity to adapt the learning process to their own needs and specific life phases (Barnett, 2014) {2}. Also, it is due to an objective desire to respond to new issues associated with the worldwide pandemic and, as a result of these restrictions, in a range of public life areas. Despite this, there are a number of professionals who are concerned about the potentially adverse impacts that could result from incorporating contemporary technologies into the learning process. "While it may appear that the changes that are taking place in the globe at an extraordinary speed are terrifying, the opportunities that are becoming available turn out to be exhilarating."

It is essential that we do not lose sight of the fact that each of these technologies is a tool that was created by people, for people, with the intention of shaping the future in a way that will be to the advantage of all of civilization. (Klaus Schwab and the World Economic Forum's 2016 report titled "The Fourth Industrial Revolution") {3} it should come as no

surprise that the development of innovative technology has had an impact on many facets of contemporary life, and education is not an exception to this rule. The use of several recently developed pieces of technology is becoming increasingly prevalent in today's educational practices as a part of an ongoing endeavor to enhance the effectiveness of classroom instruction. (Jensen, J.; Kummer, T. & Godoy, P., 2015) {4}.

Yet, educators should keep in mind that the fundamental pedagogical purposes of scientific models are to support students in their learning and to boost students' ability to identify answers to issues. This is true regardless of the context in which the lessons are being delivered. During the time of the epidemic, everyone was aware that taking classes through the internet is not a sufficient replacement for attending classes in a conventional venue. This was a common sentiment. The inescapable transition into the world of online learning has brought with it a number of obstacles for those working in the sector of international education. A lesson that is presented online that focuses on the responsibility and self-motivation of the student. Since students always keep the classroom under control, and they feel they have the backing of their teachers.

In the year 2012, two chemistry instructors named Jonathan Bergmann and Aaron Sams from Woodland Park, Colorado, United States, were the first to use the phrase "inverted classroom" in their own classroom. They accomplished this with the purpose of guaranteeing that students who were absent from a class would still be able to follow along with the course through the recorded lectures that they had started publishing online in the year 2012. This was the most innovative and fruitful new approach to the distribution of educational content.

Thus, what exactly does it mean to have a classroom that is "flipped"? The instructional method known as "flipped learning," which is also referred to as "mixed learning" at times, is a type of "blended learning" in which in-class activities and assigned homework are alternated. The flipped classroom changes the context and way of working for both the teacher and the students, inside and outside the classroom (Bishop & Verleger, 2013) {5}.

The flipped classroom is a pedagogical model in which the instructor shares predetermined digital resources with students through a platform outside the classroom; related content is also taught asynchronously through this outside platform (Bergmann & Sams, 2012) {6}. A survey of studies that have been published demonstrates that the term "flipped class" has been used in the research papers written by researchers from both the United States and other countries (M. Lage, G. Platt & M. Treglia, G.M. Novak, J. Bergmann, J. Overmyer & B. Wilie, M. Gilboy, S. Heinerichs & G. Pazzaglia, K. Muldrow, J. Graney, H. Hung, H. Marshall) {7}. The traditional method of instructing students gets flipped on its head with the implementation of the flipped classroom (also known as "flipped class"). The process of shifting activities that would have ordinarily taken place within the classroom to the space immediately outside of it and vice versa is referred to as "inverting the classroom." The phrase "inverting the classroom" refers to this technique. Although Bishop and Verleger mentioned in 2013 that the FC only reflects a re-ordering of "in-class" and "out-of-classroom" events, the FC now indicates that such activities have been re-ordered.. In light of this, Bishop and Verleger classified the FC as "...an educational technique that comprises of two parts: interactive group learning

activities inside the classroom, and direct computer-based individual training outside the classroom" [5]. It is likely that utilizing FC will prove to be an effective means of assisting students in the process of learning new information (Hattie, 2008; Schwerdt & Wupperman, 2010) {8}. The flipped classroom approach has received special attention in the educational design of blended learning (Thai, De Wever, & Valcke, 2017) {9}, and this has proven effective (Strelan, Osborn, & Palmer, 2020) {10}, also in combination with blended learning (Baepler, Walker, & Driessen, 2014) {11}. In addition to this, flipping classrooms can be considered an inventive new method to mixed learning that places an emphasis on receiving an education that is comprehensive. Some researchers have already taken results: Although the flipped classroom has many advantages and positive effects (Akçayir & Akçayir, 2018; Blair et al., 2016; González-Gómez et al., 2016; Love et al., 2014; Nouri, 2016; Roach, 2014) Goodwin and Miller (2013) {12} point out that the evidence on the inverted model is still to come, recognizing that there is currently no large scientific research indicating exactly how effective classrooms that follow this model are. Also, Fadol et al. (2018) and Lopes and Soares (2018) {13} consider that further studies on different subjects and instructional contexts are needed to gain a better understanding of this new flipped classroom technique.

Paulson, Dr. Adriana Banu, Dr. Brian Utter and Dr. Bill Ingham of James Madison University state that they have seen their student pre-test/post-test growth increase from 20-25 % to 35% since they began flipping their college physics classes (Gorton, 2014) {14}. Performing a quantitative analysis of the above results, we can conclude that after the completion of the experiment, 72% of the students in the experimental group had a high level of knowledge (grades 4 and 5), while initially this percentage was 12% (translated)(N. I. Isupova, T. N. Suvorova Gamification of the educational process using the "flipped classroom" technology) {15}.

1. It is the student's responsibility to independently study any new material at home. When a flipped classroom is well articulated, it can stimulate and excite learners to be actively involved in the learning process instead of being docile receivers of information (Hunley, 2016) {16} The components that make up this approach include working with presentations, working with recommended books, working with site resources given by the instructor, and watching video lectures. Alzain (2015) {17} also added that flipped classrooms can lead to improve intellectual abilities of learners.
2. Students work on projects in the classroom that require them to collaborate with one another and show engagement with one another (for example, interactive activities, group discussions, etc.). Thus, prior to attending class, students individually engage with content materials, often via prerecorded lectures, prescribed readings, study guides, interactive videos, simulations and cases, and in-class pedagogies such as interactive engagement, just-in-time teaching, and peer instruction (Berrett, 2012) {18}.
3. The role of the teacher is comparable to that of an observer; it is their responsibility to offer timely remarks and evaluate the job. According to Baker [19], who was one of the pioneers in the work related to this area, the teacher must be a "guide on the side" (Baker, J. W. (2000) {19} "The "classroom flip": Using web course management tools

to become the guide by the side." Paper presented at the 11th International Conference on College Teaching and Learning, Jacksonville, FL.).

The most important tactic for putting this learning model into reality is based on the following pedagogical tenet: direct learning takes place outside of the classroom, and the classroom is utilized for practice and application of the subject instead. Danker (2015) and Saglam and Arslan (2018) {20} show that students who followed the flipped classroom model had a better attitude than did those students who followed traditional instruction. The term "inverted class" can be understood in a broad sense to refer to the utilization of information technology (IT) in the restructuring of the fundamental components of the educational process. Zainuddin and Attaran (2016), White et al. (2017), Murillo et al. (2019), and Zheng et al. (2020) {21} also report changes in attitude and improved student engagement and involvement among their results. The "flipped classroom" paradigm is based on a revised version of B. Bloom's taxonomy, and it means that students focus on comprehending higher forms of cognitive activity (application, analysis, synthesis, and assessment) while the material is still being presented in the lesson.

The model's main objective is to work on the higher-level skills of Bloom's taxonomy (i.e., create, analyze, and evaluate) by making the student take a much more active role in their learning process (Berenguer, 2016) {22}. This indicates that students engage in lower levels of cognitive activity (such as acquiring knowledge outside of the classroom), but that they do so in order to concentrate on the comprehension of higher kinds of cognitive activity. In a flipped classroom, students' attention is enhanced as the class is participatory and there is a change from the normal sit and listen to individual learning (Jose and Jorge 2020; Birgili et al., 2021) {23}. Students' understanding of concepts becomes better in the flipped classroom (Hava 2021) {24}. By the educational trend Kazakhstan and Russia also actively use flipped classroom methodology. Having studied the theoretical material at home using all the sources including video lessons on YouTube and at their own pace thus nobody reminded about time, nobody hurried them, the students came to the class more confident, more aware of themselves, ready to cooperate (E. Fedossoval S. Aubakirova Bulletin of the M. Kozybayev NKSU 2019) {25}. The results obtained in the course of the study indicate that the technology «inverted classroom» is a promising direction for the development of a system of mixed learning of students. (Students' Attitude to Blended Learning Using the «Flipped Classroom» Technology I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation) {26}. As a result of this, I came up with the following question to guide my investigation:

- 1) Is the 'flipped learning' approach utilized by the NIS a trustworthy mode of instruction for the subject of physics?
- 2) How am I able to figure out how much it costs?

To get things started, I'm going to talk about the physics classes that are offered at NIS. It is the purpose of the more advanced course in physics to broaden students' understanding of physics as a natural science, the methods and methodology of scientific knowledge, as well as the function and interaction of theory and experiment in the process of acquiring new information. The FC studied student feedback was very positive, and indicated a high level of student involvement with the new approach (Flipping the CS1 and CS2 classrooms in Central Asia Benjamin Tyler, Madina Abdrakhmanova) {27}. The development of the student's observational skills is the primary focus of the physics course, with the ultimate objective being for the student to be able to recognize natural occurrences, explain and synthesise data, and make use of measuring tools when conducting research on physical phenomena. From many points of view the application and incorporation of flipped classroom into educational process would be of benefit both for teachers and students at the same time (Nabiyeva K.M. The Incorporation of flipped classroom into the educational process in Kazakhstani English language classrooms) {28}. Students are given the opportunity to plan and carry out an experiment as part of the content that is covered in the in-depth course. The experiment's results, which are gathered and analyzed, are used to determine an empirical relationship based on the findings of the experiment. Students who have had the opportunity to receive preparation for an in-depth general education in physics are able to apply the knowledge they have acquired to explain the causes of a wide variety of natural phenomena and processes, the operating principles of significant technical installations, as well as to create models and make predictions; (adilet.zan.kz) {29}

As part of the research program that the NIS will be doing on the topic of "Physics," the following goals will be attempted to be achieved:

- To provide a collection of information, methods, and strategies that are unique to science and technology;
- To stimulate and provide the solution to the problem of education by giving opportunities for students to undertake scientific research and apply their creative works in a global environment.
- To provide students with the chance to apply and make use of a body of knowledge, methodologies, and approaches that are unique to the fields of science and technology.
- The acquisition of skills in the process of systematically examining, assessing, and arranging scientific data and information.
- Getting to an understanding of the value of effective teamwork and the unrestricted interchange of ideas while carrying out scientific research; this is essential.

Through their study of physics, students will gain an understanding of the following:

how to analyze the possibilities and constraints connected with modern science and scientists • the interrelationship between scientific fields and the multifaceted nature of the scientific process 204 hours of schooling are required per year for 11th grade because there are 34 weeks in a year and each of the 6 lessons lasts for 40 minutes.

186 academic hours a year is equivalent to a 31-week school year for the 12th grade, which is divided into six classes that are each 40 minutes long.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The study was carried out during the fall semester of 2022 at NIS HB and PHM in Shymkent using subject Physics, for students majoring in scientific fields. The Physics were taught back to back at 9:30am and 11:00am on Tuesdays, Thursdays and Fridays. The earlier class was designated as the control and the later class as the treatment by the flip of a coin. Since truly random sampling of the individual participants was impossible, but a quantitative comparison of two groups was made, the study was quasi-experimental.

Participants

Each section had an enrollment of 60 students for a total of 120 students. In the control section, one student who was under 18 years of age and two students elected not to participate were omitted from the study leaving 57 participants. In the treatment section, 2 students elected not to participate and were omitted from the study leaving 58 participants. The control group consisted of 5 freshmen, 26 sophomores, 16 juniors, and 10 seniors of which 24 were males and 33 were females. The treatment group had a 19 similar composition with 3 freshmen, 31 sophomores, 18 juniors, and 6 seniors of which 22 were males and 36 were females.

In a quasi-experimental study of this type it is important to show that the two groups are equivalent at the onset of the study in order to eliminate possible threats to the validity of the results. The composite Laboratory work scores for both sections were compared using independent samples t-test and found to be statistically the same ($p=0.43$). A similar comparison was made with the Dynamics Baseline Test, or DBT, pretest scores for each section, and those results also indicated that the two groups were statistically identical ($p=0.68$).

Instrumentation

Quantifiable data to test the research hypotheses were collected using two tools. To measure physics knowledge gains, a pre/posttest was administered using the DBT. This 20 question multiple choice test measures the conceptual understanding of basic mechanics covered in an introductory physics classroom and is widely used in physics education research. Please see the Appendix A for a reproduction of this instrument. In addition, an instructor generated unit exam covering the material was used to measure physics knowledge. This exam included six multiple choice questions of a conceptual nature and nine open-ended problems where students are required to show their work. A copy of the unit test is included in Appendix B.

Procedure

Preparation for the study began during the summer session of 2021. During the June summer session, lecture video recordings of my PH 11 grade class were made. These 20 were edited via Camtasia 2 into convenient ten to twenty minute segments and uploaded to YouTube for later access by the inverted class.

Prior to the start of classes in the fall of 2021, approval to conduct the study was obtained from the NIS COP. On the first day of class, the students in both sections were informed about the study and consent forms were collected. A copy of the consent form is included in the appendix. The DBT pretest was administered at this time.

Once the two participating sections were determined and initial data was collected, instruction began as normal. The first unit covering materials and gravity, the conservation laws were covered in the traditional manner for both classes. To further establish the similarity of the two sections, an independent samples t-test was performed and both groups were found to be statistically identical in regard to scores on the instructor generated first exam ($p=0.92$). Starting in week 5, after the first exam, the experiment began in earnest. The second unit, covering the the conservation laws was covered traditionally in one section while the inverted model was utilized in the other.

The videos recorded and edited during the summer were uploaded to YouTube so that the students in the flipped classroom would have access to them. These videos, along with standard textbook (Giancoli & Boyle, 2013) {30} reading, were assigned as homework for this section with two to three assigned to be watched before each class meeting. Class time was spent engaging the students in the material. Each 75 minute class meeting opened with a brief review of the required videos answering any questions that may have arisen as the students watched.

Then approximately fifteen to twenty 21minutes were spent on peer instruction similar to the method described by Crouch and Mazur (2001). {31} a multiple choice question designed to probe the concepts covered in the video was presented to the class. Students think about the answer and indicate their response by holding up a piece of paper with a large bold letter indicating their response. The students were then told to discuss and defend their answer choice with fellow students in groups of two to three and were then re-pollled. This allowed the instructor to survey the comprehension of the class and offer targeted feedback.

In some cases, if there was still a sizable portion of the class who missed the mark, a second round of discussion was completed before finally revealing and discussing the correct answer. The remaining bulk of class time was spent in small group problem solving. Students worked in groups of three to four to work through problems created by the instructor or pulled from the course textbook with the instructor circulating through the class giving guidance when needed.

Meanwhile, the control group was taught using traditional methods. Textbook reading was assigned to be completed before lecture, and all problems completed in class by the experimental group were assigned as homework to be completed individually after the

lecture covering the concepts relating to those specific problems. Additionally, the conceptual multiple choice questions with explanations were provided as supplemental study tools to be examined outside of class. Class time was spent with the instructor lecturing and working through example problems. My lecture style could be described as quite interactive with frequent questioning of the students, but the level of individual engagement was much less when compared to the experimental group. The idea was to keep the material covered, the lectures viewed, and the exercises completed for both

22 sections to be as similar as possible. This is why I chose to use my own recorded lectures to implement the inverted class model instead of referring students to some of the pre-made lecture substitutes such as Khan Academy. I feel that this helped ensure that any differences in the measured outcomes of the two sections can be more readily attributed to the implementation of the inverted model rather than some confounding factor.

At the end of the unit, both sections were administered the same unit exam as well as the DBT posttest. These DBT scores were then used in conjunction with the pretest scores from the beginning of the semester to produce a normalized gain score (Hake, 1998). {32} this normalized gain takes into account the available room for improvement and is a standard measure of physics content knowledge and is calculated by the following formula:

$$\frac{\text{postscore}\% - \text{prescore}\%}{100 - \text{prescore}\%}$$

Data Analysis

To address the first hypothesis, an independent samples t-test was used to detect any significant difference between the normalized gain scores for the control and treatment sections. This method of analysis requires that the data meets the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance. Both were checked and found to be satisfactory.

Likewise, an independent samples t-test was used to evaluate the second hypothesis regarding the exam scores. When normality was checked, the treatment group failed to meet the assumption due to a significant negative skew. To address this, the data was transformed and the square of the exam scores was used to make the comparison. The transformed data met all necessary assumptions.

IBM's SPSS Version 21 was used for all data analysis. Significance for all hypotheses and relevant tests was based on an alpha level of 0.05.

RESULTS

Hypothesis One

The first hypothesis tested by this study stated that the students exposed to the flipped model would demonstrate a greater level of physics learning as measured by the normalized gain on the widely used Dynamics Baseline Test. One student in the control

group and three students in the treatment group failed to complete the DBT posttest so their data was omitted from the analysis. Summary statistics for the DBT pre and post tests are summarized below in Table 2.

Table 2: DBT Results

		N	M	SD
Control	Pretest raw score	57	11,3	3,02
	Posttest raw score	57	14,8	2,43
	Pretest percentage	57	56,5	13,26
	Posttest percentage	57	74	12,16
	normalized gain	57	0,37	0,295
Treatment	Pretest raw score	58	10,72	2,38
	Posttest raw score	58	14,1	3,12
	Pretest percentage	58	53,6	11,91
	Posttest percentage	58	70,43	15,62
	normalized gain	58	0,335	0,358

Paired samples t-tests indicated there was a statistically significant increase in the DBT scores from the pre to posttest for both the control group, $t(56) = 4.07$, $p < 0.001$, and the treatment group, $t(56) = 6.24$, $p < 0.001$.

This indicates that both groups improved their physics knowledge as measured by the DBT, but an analysis of the normalized gain score was need to shed light on any differences between the two groups. Although the mean normalized gain was indeed higher for the treatment group, the independent samples t-test indicated that there was no statistically significant difference between the control and treatment groups; $t(112) = 1.67$, $p = 0.097$.

Hypothesis Two

The second hypothesis examined by this study was also concerned with differences in physics learning between the flipped and traditional methods but as measured by the grades on the instructor-generated exam testing the material covered during the study.

The mean scores on the exam from both sections were typical for this course. Like the DBT results, analysis of the squared exam grades revealed no statistically significant difference between the control and treatment groups; $t(116) = 1.07$, $p = 0.214$. Summary statistics for the raw and transformed exam grades are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Unit exam results

		N	M	SD
Control	Exam Raw	57	75,8	12,3
	Exam Squared	57	58,99	1916
Treatment	Exam Raw	58	78,6	12
	Exam Squared	58	6321	1850

CONCLUSION

This study contributes to the growing corpus of scholarly research on the flipped classroom and supports the notion that the flipped learning paradigm may be used in school education. The high school policy of giving teachers flexibility in how they taught their sections might have been a significant confounding element in the performance of the flipped classroom approach, and the study's conclusions should be read with caution.

It did, however, show that students in novice teachers' flipped portions outperformed students in traditional sections. Furthermore, the flipped classroom approach was most effective with teachers that excel in inquiry-based and cooperative learning.

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